

Management

JOB SATISFACTION IN STATE BANK OF INDIA

Dr. A. Thangaswamy ^{*1}

^{*1} Assistant Professor & Head of Commerce, Pioneer Kumaraswamy College, Nagercoil- 3,
INDIA

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.59377

ABSTRACT

The present study “A study on job satisfaction of bank employees with reference to State Bank of India, Kanyakumari District” is an empirical study based on the survey conducted through census method among the employees working in the State Bank of India in Kanyakumari District. The primary data related to the employees working in the State Bank of India in Kanyakumari District have been collected through a pre-structured questionnaire, prepared by the researcher. The questionnaire contains questions pertaining to personal data, socio economic data, employment details and satisfaction in work.

Keywords:

Employees, Job Satisfaction, State Bank of India.

Cite This Article: Dr. A. Thangaswamy, “JOB SATISFACTION IN STATE BANK OF INDIA”, International Journal of Research – Granthaalayah, Vol. 4, No. 7: SE (2016): 55-61.

1. INTRODUCTION

Job satisfaction is a psychological phenomenon which explains the state of mind of the workers related to their job. Psychological mental state of the workers in relation to their job may be positive or negative. While a set of workers in any organisation have positive job satisfaction, others may have negative job satisfaction in their job. Therefore, in every organisation there are workers with positive and negative job satisfaction. It indicates that the job satisfaction of workers differs from individual to individual. It could also be noticed that in every organisation, there are workers with different levels of job satisfaction. Differing levels of job satisfaction have a positive or negative impact on the work performance of the employees in their job. Hence the differing levels of job satisfaction is a serious issue to be noticed immediately. The present chapter explains the differing levels of job satisfaction among different sets of employees in State Bank of India in Kanyakumari District. It helps to locate the set of workers who are dissatisfied in their job in State Bank of India in Kanyakumari District. Further locating of such workers who are dissatisfied in their job is helpful to suggest suitable measures to overcome job dissatisfaction. Because job dissatisfaction of the individuals has serious consequences in the

organisation. Primary data elicited through the structured questionnaire have been used for the preparation of this paper.

2. METHODOLOGY

The present study “A study on job satisfaction of bank employees with reference to State Bank of India, Kanyakumari District” is an empirical study based on the survey conducted through census method among the employees working in the State Bank of India in Kanyakumari District. The primary data related to the employees working in the State Bank of India in Kanyakumari District have been collected through a pre-structured questionnaire, prepared by the researcher (a copy of which is appended in Appendix I).

The questionnaire contains questions pertaining to personal data, socio economic data, employment details and satisfaction in work. Before finalising the questionnaire, discussions were held with a selected number of bank employees working in the study area. Based on the discussion, the questionnaire was modified. Then a pilot study was conducted with 30 bank employees equally representing official, clerical and substaff category. The pilot study helped to pretest the questionnaire. After taking into account the results of pretesting, the reliability testing and validation of the questionnaire were done. The difficulties in answering some of the questions were the modified as suggested by the bank employees. On the basis of this rigorous process, the questionnaire was finally shaped, and the same was used for data collection.

The secondary data relating to the study have been collected from various journals, bulletins, magazines, newspapers, books, periodicals, internet and unpublished documents.

3. JOB SATISFACTION MEASUREMENT MODEL

In the present study, the investigator used Porter’s model for measuring job satisfaction. The twenty job characteristics identified by the Porter have been used for measuring job satisfaction. All these 20 job characteristics have been used for further analysis. They are

The Porter’s model measures the job satisfaction of the bank employees with respect to 20 job characteristics in three stages by using three types of questions namely a, b, c (a) How much he/she finds about characteristics in the job (Perception) (b) How much he/she would like to have the characteristics in the job (Aspiration) (c) How important are these characteristics for him/her? The above three questions measure three attitudes of the employees with respect to 20 identified job characteristics namely the perception of the employee about a particular job characteristics. The aspiration of the employee about particular job characteristics. The importance what the employee attributes to a particular job characteristics.

The above attitudinal survey was conducted with respect to all the 20 job characteristics. Every respondent was asked to answer a, b, c by encircling a number on the rating scale ranging from 5 to 1 for each characteristic in three situations. Encircling the lowest number indicates that the respondent attributes minimum value to the particular job characteristics and encircling the highest number represents that the respondent attributes a high value to a particular job characteristic.

Then the discrepancy scores for each of the 20 job characteristics were calculated as the difference between aspiration and perception (b-a). The result may be positive or negative. Then the resultant scores were multiplied by the corresponding scores of perceived importance (c) attributed by each respondent for each characteristic. This was done for each of the 20 job characteristics. Then the final scores of c (b-a) were summed up to calculate the overall job satisfaction of the State Bank of India employees in Kanyakumari District.

4. SCALING TECHNIQUE

In the study the variables which cause job satisfaction are analysed through scaling technique. There are 31 variables identified as influencing job satisfaction. All these variables have been observed in the study. There are 31 statements (Positive and negative) depicting the influence of the variable on job satisfaction with Likert type 5 point scale was evolved. Thus each statement has five alternatives from which the respondents have to choose the one which expresses his/her response.

To get the total job satisfaction score of a respondent for positive statement five points were given for Highly Influence state, four for Influence state, three for No Influence state, two for Negative influence state and one for Highly Negative Influence state. Likewise for negative statements, highly influence state response was given a weightage of 1, Influence state response was assigned the weightage of 2, No Influence state had the weightage of 3, Negative Influence state of weightage had 4 and Highly Negative Influence state had the weightage of 5. Thus the total job satisfaction score of a respondent is calculated by adding up the scores marked by the respondent with respect to 31 statements.

5. MEASUREMENT OF JOB SATISFACTION

Among the available models, Porter's model is identified to be the best model to measure the level of job satisfaction. The Porter's model measures the job satisfaction of the bank employees through the answers by the employees for three questions asked. The three answers to the questions measure the perception, aspiration and the importance given by the employee to each of the identified job characteristics as outlined by Porter. The questions raised before the employees in State Bank of India reveal the state of mind related to job satisfaction which are represented in the questionnaire by the alphabet a, b and c. The questions are (a) How much he/she finds about the characteristics in the job? (Perception) (b) How much he/she would like to have the characteristics in the job? (Aspiration) (c) How much important are these characteristics for him/her? (importance).

The question with the letter 'a' represents the perception of the employee about job characteristics related to his / her job which elicits information about the perception of job about particular job characteristics. Similarly the question represented by the alphabet 'b' represents the aspiration of the employee about a particular job characteristic and the question represented by the alphabet 'c' measures the importance what the employee attribute to a particular job characteristic in his / her job.

For each item of job characteristics a respondent was asked to answer three states of their mind represented by a, b, c by circling a number on the rating scale ranging from 5 to 1. Encircling a lower valued number represents the lower significance the respondent attributes to a particular job characteristics and encircling a higher number represents higher significance the employee attributes to a job characteristic. Then the discrepancy scores were calculated as the difference between aspiration and perception (b-a). The result may be positive or negative. The symbol is neglected and sign does not have any significance. Both types of scores were multiplied by the corresponding score of perceived importance (c) of a respondent for each characteristic. This was done for each of 20 job characteristics. The scores of c (b-a) were summed up to calculate the overall job satisfaction of each State Bank of India employee in Kanyakumari District.

Thus an employee with a very high level of job satisfaction gets a maximum score of (+) 400 that is 20 job characteristics $\square 5$ (5-1) and another employee with total dissatisfaction can get a score of (-) 400 that is 20 characteristics $\square 5$ (1-5). So the job satisfaction scoring range varies between +400 and -400.

6. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The main objective of this article is:

- To measure the level of job satisfaction of bank employees in the State Bank of India in Kanyakumari District.

7. ANALYSIS & FINDINGS

JOB SATISFACTION IN STATE BANK OF INDIA

Job satisfaction scores as measured through Porter's model presents the level of job satisfaction of the employees in State Bank of India in Kanyakumari District. The actual job satisfaction scores scored by the employees of State Bank of India in Kanyakumari District ranged between 1 and 358.

It is interesting to find that in the study area none has negatively scored. It indicates that no employee working in State Bank of India in Kanyakumari District is totally dissatisfied in his / her job.

Table 1 exhibits the job satisfaction scores scored by the employees working in State Bank of India in Kanyakumari District.

Table 1: Job Satisfaction Scores of Employees in State Bank of India

Scores	No. of Employees	Percentage
Less than 50	8	2.91
50 – 100	61	22.19
100 – 150	32	11.63
150 – 200	10	3.63
200 – 250	134	48.73

250 – 300	6	2.18
Above 300	24	8.73
Total	275	100

Source: Primary data

It is evident from table 1 that 22.19 per cent of the employees working in State Bank of India in Kanyakumari District had the job satisfaction score 50 to 100. It is further made clear that only 59.64 percent of the employees had the job satisfaction score above 200 which indicates that they have scored above 50 per cent of the maximum score.

Further analysis of the frequency of job satisfaction scores through statistical tools such as mean and standard deviation helps for a further analysis of job satisfaction among employees of State

Bank of India in Kanyakumari District. The calculated mean (\bar{X}) and standard deviation (σ) on the raw job satisfaction frequencies gives the results as $\bar{X} = 262$ $\sigma = 74$

The calculated mean and standard deviation were used to fix the boundaries for making further analysis. The boundary levels fixed for further analysis are

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Upper boundary for low level satisfaction} &= \bar{X} - \sigma \\ &= 262 - 74 = 188 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Lower boundary for high level satisfaction} &= \bar{X} + \sigma \\ &= 262 + 74 = 336 \end{aligned}$$

Thus on the basis of the job satisfaction scores scored by the employees, and the boundaries fixed through the statistical measures, those who scored below 188 are regarded as employees with lower level of job satisfaction, and those with job satisfaction score above 336 are regarded as employees with higher level of job satisfaction and those with scores between 188 and 336 are regarded as employees with a medium level of job satisfaction.

On the basis of the above yardstick employees in State Bank of India, namely officers, clerical staff and sub staff are classified and categorized into three groups namely employees with higher level of job satisfaction, employees with medium level of job satisfaction and employees with lower level of job satisfaction. The details of employees falling under these categories of job satisfaction are presented in table 2.

Table 2: Level of Job Satisfaction among the Employees of State Bank of India

Sl. No.	Level of Job Satisfaction	Officers %	Clerical Staff %	Sub staff %	Total %

1	Low	17	28.3	43	30.7	51	68	111	40.3
2	Medium	34	56.7	85	60.7	21	28	140	50.9
3	High	9	15.0	12	8.6	3	4	24	8.8
	Total	60	100	140	100	75	100	275	100

Source: Primary data

It is clear from table 2 that among the officers of State Bank of India 56.7 per cent had medium level of job satisfaction and 15 per cent had higher level of job satisfaction. In the case of clerical staff 30.7 per cent had lower level of job satisfaction and 60.7 per cent had medium level of job satisfaction.

But among sub staff 68 per cent had lower level of job satisfaction which is higher than that of the officers and clerical staff. Clerical and sub staff had nearly the same level of job satisfaction, that is, 8 per cent had higher level of job satisfaction.

8. REFERENCES

- [1] Arya, P.P., "Work Satisfaction and its Correlates", *Indian Journal of Industrial Relations*, 1984, Vol. 20, Issue No. 1.
- [2] Baldev R. Sharma, "Determinants of Job Satisfaction among Bank Employees", *Management and Labour Studies*, 1979, Vol. 5, Issue No. 2.
- [3] Golden, S. A. R. (2015). *Regional Imbalance affecting quality of e-banking services with special reference to Tuticorin District-An Analysis*. *International Journal of Research*, 2(3), 788-798.
- [4] Golden, S. A. R. (2016). *Mobile Subscribers' Satisfaction Towards Offers*. *Shanlax International Journal of Arts, Science & Humanities*. Golden, SAR *Mobile Subscribers' attitude Towards Service Tariff with Special Reference to Tuticorin Dist*.
- [5] Golden, S. A. R., & Gopalakrishnan, D. *Subscriber's Perception Towards Customer Care Service In Mobile Telecommunication With Special Reference To Tuticorin City*. Chief Patron Chief Patron.
- [6] Golden, S. A. R., & Regi, S. B. (2015). *Satisfaction of Customers towards User Friendly Technological Services offered by Public and Private Sector banks at Palayamkottai, Tirunelveli District*. *International Journal of Research*, 2(3), 775-787.
- [7] Kailasam, S.P., *Job Satisfaction of bank employees - A Comparative Study of Nationalised and Non-Nationalised Commercial Bank with special reference to Coimbatore*, 2002.
- [8] Percy Rose, B. *A study on Employee's Job Satisfaction in Neyveli Lignite Corporation Limited, Neyveli*, 2005.
- [9] Rajeswari, A., "A Comparative Study on Job Satisfaction of Women Employees of Public Sector Banks and LIC in Tirunelveli District", 2000.

- [10] Rama, A., “Job satisfaction of Bank Employees - A Study with Reference to Kamarajar District”, Madurai Kamaraj University, 1994.
- [11] Regi, S. B., & Golden, S. A. R. (2014). Customer Preference Towards Innovative Banking Practices Available In State Bank Of India At Palayamkottai. *Sankhya International Journal Of Management And Technology*, 3 (11 (A)), 31, 33.
- [12] Regi, S. B., & Golden, S. A. R. (2014). Reforms In Insurance Sector In India-A Empirical Study. *Review Of Research*, 3 (9), 1, 5.
- [13] Sinha, D. and Nair, R.R., “A Study of Job Satisfaction in Factory Workers”, *Indian Journal of Social Work*, 1965, Vol. 26, Issue No. 1.
- [14] Sinha, D., “Job Satisfaction in Office and Manual Workers”, *Indian Journal of Social Work*, 1958, Vol. 19.
- [15] Swatantra Kumar, Singh, D.P.N. and Verma, S.K., “Expectations and Job Satisfaction of Officers and Supervisors in a Public Sector Undertaking”, *Indian Journal of Industrial Relations*, 1982, Vol. 5.
- [16] Thakur, C.P., “Fringe Benefits and Appropriate Management - An Empirical Study”, *Indian Journal of Industrial Relations*, 1978, Vol. 14, Issue No. 1.
- [17] Thamarai Kannan et al., “Job Satisfaction of Employees of Sakthi Sugar Mills”, *Kisan World*, 2008, Vol. 35, Issue No. 8.